

Some reactions with quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid anhydride. Synthesis of quinazolinoquinoxalines and quinazolino[2,3:6,1]pyridazino[4,5-*b*]quinoxalines

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Many derivatives of quinazolinoquinoxalines and quinazolino[2,3:6,1]pyridazino[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline have been prepared starting from quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid anhydride.

Both quinoxaline and quinazolines possess various biological and pharmacological activities¹. In continuation of our work², it was considered of interest to synthesize new quinoxalines containing quinazoline moiety which might possess biological activity.

Thus, condensation³ of quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid anhydride **1** with anthranilic acid or methyl anthranilate in boiling ethanol led to opening of the lactone ring to give 2-amidoquinoxaline-3-carboxylic acid derivatives **2a,b**. While heating **1** with anthranilic acid or methyl anthranilate under fusion condition afforded 2-aminoquinoxaline derivatives **3a,b**. Treatment of **2a,b** with acetic anhydride through cyclization gave quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboximides **4a,b** which when reacted with the amines under fusion condition produced quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxamides **5a-e**. Similarly, dehydration of **3a** with acetic anhydride effected cyclization to furnish 2-[(3,1)-4-oxobenzoxazin-2-yl]quinoxalin **6**. Hydrazinolysis of **6** in ethanol afforded 2-(3-amino-4-oxoquinazolin-2-yl)quinoxaline **7**. The structure **7** was supported by spectral data and by an independent synthesis of the same product from **3b** and hydrazine hydrate in refluxing butanol. Also, hydrazinolysis of **2b** in *n*-butanol yielded 11,13-dioxo-11,12,13-trihydroquinazolino[2,3:6,1]pyridazino[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline **9**. Compound **9** was expectedly produced via the formation 3-aminoquinazoline derivative **8** as intermediate which readily cyclized through elimination of water (Scheme 1).

On the other hand, the cyclization of the diamides **5c,d** with hydrazine hydrate in *n*-butanol furnished the corresponding *N*-aminoquinazolinoquinoxaline derivatives **11a,b**. The structure of **11** was confirmed by its synthesis through dehydration of **5a,b** with acetic anhydride, which afforded the benzoxazine derivative **10** followed by hydrazinolysis. Then the 3-aminoquinazolinoquinoxaline **7** was taken as starting material for different reactions to synthesize condensed heterocycles. Thus, condensation of **7** with aromatic aldehydes yielded 2-[3-arylideneimino-4-quinazolin-

2-yl]quinoxalines **12a,b**, **13**, **14a,b**. Treatment of **7** with aryl isocyanates in pyridine produced the urea derivatives **15a,b**. In addition, when the benzoxazine derivative **6** was condensed with formamide or aromatic amines, the quinazolinoquinoxaline derivatives **16**, **17a,b** were formed (Scheme 2).

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra were determined on a JASCO FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra were measured on a Varian EM-360 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Shimadzu-GC MS-QP 100 EX instrument. TLC was carried out on silica gel (MN-kieselgel G) with ethyl acetate : *n*-hexane as the developer and scanned under uv-light (254 nm). Microanalyses were performed at Microanalytical Unit, Cairo University. All new compounds showed satisfactory analytical data for C, H and N.

Compounds 2a,b : A mixture of quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride (0.01 mol) and anthranilic acid or methyl anthranilate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and the resulting solids were crystallized from appropriate solvents : **2a** (72%), m.p. 285°; **2b** (70%), 190°, *m/z* 351 (M⁺, 10%), 307 (55), 248 (57), 220 (7), 178 (6), 130 (100), 102 (56), 76 (24).

Compounds 3a,b : A mixture of quinoxaline-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride (0.01 mol) and anthranilic acid or methyl anthranilate (0.1 mol) was fused at 160–170° for 15 min and triturated with ethanol. The resulting solids were crystallized from appropriate solvents **3a** (77%), m.p. 260°; **3b** (78%), 160°, ν_{\max} 3182 (NH), 1706, 1681 (CO), 1585 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ 3.99 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.25–8.84 (8H, m, ArH), 9.55 (1H, s, 2-quinoxaliny), 12.83 (1H, s, NH, exchanged with D₂O).

Compounds 4a,b : A solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (20 ml) was refluxed for 15 min to give the

Note

Scheme 1

dicarboximide derivatives : **4a** (69%), m.p. 265° , m/z 319 (44), 303 (100), 275 (45), 246 (55), 219 (11), 146 (96), 90 (65), 76 (11); **4b** (65%), 235° , ν_{max} 1710 (CO), 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ 3.96 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.83–8.20 (8H, m, ArH).

Compounds 5a–e : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and the requisite amine (0.01 mol) was fused at $160\text{--}170^\circ$ for 15 min to give the products : **5a** (67%), m.p. $>300^\circ$, m/z 443 (M^+ , 1%), 69 (100), 305 (12), 256 (9), 203 (9), 149 (31), 129 (40); **5b** (66%), 245° , δ 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.99 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 6.67–8.78 (12H, m, ArH), 10.61, 12.76 (2H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O); **5c** (64%) 250° , δ 3.30 (4H, s, 2 CH_3 morpholinyl N), 3.77 (4H, s, 2 CH_2 morpholinyl O), 4.2–4.8 (1H, hump, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 7.27–8.94 (8H, m, ArH), 13.34 (1H, s, COOH); **5d** (70%), 240° , m/z 460 (2), 309 (62), 156 (12), 149 (24), 120 (8), 76 (14), 68 (100); **5e** (72%), 207° .

Compounds 6 and 10a,b : A solution of **3a** and **5a,b** (0.01 mol) separately in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h to give the products : **6** (71%), m.p. 240° , m/z 276 (M^+ , 8), 275 (50), 247 (11), 219 (6), 171 (5), 146 (100), 129 (15), 90 (36), 69 (66); **10a** (71%), $>300^\circ$; **10b**

(73%), 260° .

Compounds 7 and 11a,b. Method A : A mixture of **3b** or **5c,d** (0.01 mol) in butanol (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 2 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled to 0° for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallized to give the product **7** (79%), m.p. 205° ; **11a** (68%), $>300^\circ$; **11b** (73%), $>300^\circ$.

Method B : A mixture of **6** or **10** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 3 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then concentrated and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallized to give **7** and **11** (m.p. and mixed m.p.) : **7** ν_{max} 3271, 3160 (NH_2), 1678 (CO) and 1635 cm^{-1} (C=N), m/z 89 (4), 146 (100), 276 (47), 219 (6), 129 (39), 102 (28), 90 (43), 76 (19); **11a** m/z 438 (1), 315 (100), 368 (0.2), 317 (4), 230 (17), 204 (4), 145 (4), 102 (25), 76 (17), δ 3.39–3.65 (8H, br, CH_2 -morpholinyl), 7.36–8.70 (8H, m, arH); **11b** ν_{max} 3320, 3250 (NH_2, NH), 1690, 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ 5.56 (2H, s, NH_2 , exchanged with D_2O), 6.91–7.82 (12H, m, ArH), 9.21 (1H, s, NH, exchanged with D_2O).

Compound 9 : A mixture of **2b** (0.01 mol) in butanol (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%, 3 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then concentrated and cooled and the resulting solid was crystallized (70%), m.p. 250° ; ν_{max} 3261 (NH), 1678

Scheme 2

(CO) and 1635 cm⁻¹ (C=N); *m/z* 315 (100), 276 (77), 230 (23), 146 (51), 129 (71), 102 (88), 76 (86).

Compounds 12a,b : A mixture of 7 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde was fused at 160–70° for 15 min to furnish the products : **12a** (65%), m.p. 275°, *v*_{max} 1663 (CO) and 1639 cm⁻¹ (C=N); **12b** (67%), 170°.

Compound 13 : A mixture of 7 (0.01 mol) in DMF (10 ml) and benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3 h to give the product (63%), m.p. 210°, *v*_{max} 3400 (NH), 1680, 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O), δ 6.79–8.10 (13H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, quinoxaline-H), 9.61 (1H, s, NH, exchanged with D₂O).

Compounds 14a,b : A mixture of 7 (0.01 mol) and arylsulfonyl chloride (0.01 ml) in benzene/pyridine mixture (1 : 1, 20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then evaporated to residue under suction, cooled, dil. HCl added, the resulting solid washed with water and crystallized from the proper solvent to give the product : **14a** (66%), m.p. 215°, δ 2.06 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.81–8.98 (12H, m, ArH), 10.21 (1H, s, 2-quinoxalinylnyl), 12.42 (1H, s, NH); **14b** (65%), 165°.

Compounds 15a,b : A mixture of 7 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate isocyanate (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h to give the products : **15a** (70%), m.p. 242°, *m/z* 408 (65%), 380 (!), 279 (62), 251 (2), 159 (2), 144 (9), 129 (100), 102 (53); **15b** (72%), 240°, *m/z* 441 (17), 129 (100), 408 (65), 349 (15), 316 (38), 276 (86), 146

(25), 76 (25).

Compound 16 : A solution of 6 (0.01 mol) and formamide (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 h to give 16 (64%), m.p. 285°.

Compounds 17a,b : A solution of 6 (0.01 mol) and the amine (0.01 mol) was fused at 160–170° for 15 min to give the product : **17a** (66%), m.p. 215°, *m/z* 380 (0.2), 277 (18), 276 (100), 369 (0.2), 220 (0.7), 102 (20), 92 (7), 76 (4), δ 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.98–8.75 (12H, m, ArH) and 9.68 (1H, s, 2-quinoxalinylnyl); **17b** (73%), 275°.

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